

THE EFFECT OF INORGANIC COLLOIDS ON THE ELECTRO-DEPOSITION OF NICKEL ON COPPER.

BY V. S. PURI AND G. C. JUNEJA.

A quantitative study of the effect of selenium, aluminium hydroxide, ferric hydroxide, iodine and sulphur sols on the deposition of nickel on copper has been made. The first three sols considerably increase the hardness and lustre of the deposit, iodine much less and sulphur has a negative effect altogether. Explanations have been attempted for their interesting behaviour.

Puri and Bhatia (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **16**, 71) studied the effect of inorganic colloids on the electrodeposition of nickel on copper. They found the presence of silver and Prussian blue hydrosols in the bath solution to increase the lustre of the plates. Arsenious sulphide was found to have an adverse effect in so far as it gave dull looking, rough and spongy deposits. Pring and Taiton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 710), Wernick (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1920, **24**, 361) and Merce (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1913, **19**, 31) noticed similar effects in the case of organic colloids like glue, gum, gelatin, egg-albumin, etc.

The present work deals with a quantitative study of the effect of selenium, sulphur, iodine, ferric hydroxide and aluminium hydroxide sols on the deposition of nickel on copper. Explanations have been attempted for their interesting behaviour.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The bath employed in the experiments was the same as used by Puri and Bhatia (*loc. cit.*) and the plates were subjected to a preliminary treatment in the same manner with the difference that a mixture of sulphuric and nitric acids was used in the final cleaning in order to expose the crystal structure and ensure a good deposit.

The sols were rendered free of electrolytes by electro dialysis. The dialyser was prepared in the following manner.

A wide mouthed glass cylinder was filled with collodion solution which was then poured out. The cylinder was rotated horizontally till the collodion remaining on the walls of the cylinder dried up. More collodion solution was poured in. A second layer was allowed to form as before. Collodion formed a layer on the walls of the cylinder from which

it was carefully withdrawn. It was washed with distilled water. The sac thus obtained was partially filled with the colloid and put into another sac of linen of the same size. This was lowered in water containing the positive and negative electrodes. The driving force of the external voltage causes the removal of the ions of the electrolyte.

Selenium Sol.—Selenium dioxide (1 g.) was dissolved in 500 c.c. of water and 100 c.c. of 1% gelatin added to the warm solution. To this 600 c.c. of hydrazine hydrate were added drop by drop. It was kept a little below the boiling point for 15 minutes. A pink sol was formed which was found to be negatively charged.

Table I shows the effect of the sol on the electrodeposition of nickel. There is a slight increase in the weight of the metal deposited on account of a fall in the resistance of the cell. The deposit is coherent, fine grained and hard.

Addition of 5 c.c. of the sol (0.00093 g.) resulted in the reduction of the number of abrasion marks. The size of the grain is also much reduced.

Addition of 10 c.c. (0.00186 g.) of the sol increases the thickness of the deposit sufficient to cover the defects so as to cause it to take high polish. The deposit was very hard.

On the addition of 15 c.c. of the sol (0.00279 g.) the deposit ceases to be coherent as the crystal size increases. This confirms the view that there is an upper limit of the concentration beyond which the deposits obtained grow dull and spongy.

Sulphur Sol.—Sulphur dioxide was passed for 10 minutes into a saturated solution of hydrogen sulphide in water. The opaque liquid was boiled to remove sulphur dioxide. Sodium chloride was added to it and the coagulated particles were centrifuged. The supernatant liquid was removed and the solid reprecipitated in water and dialysed. There was a negative charge on the sol.

Experiments showed that there is a wide discrepancy between the theoretical and the experimental values for the metal deposited. It seems there is a large increase in the resistance of the cell. Further the anode becomes black and spongy. There was no appreciable difference with 5 c.c. and 15 c.c. of the colloid.

Iodine Sol.—Iodine crystals were added cautiously to a 2% solution of sodium hydroxide until the straw yellow liquid just began to turn red. The unreacted iodine was removed. Gum arabic (2 g.) was added at 0° and the mixture acidified with concentrated HCl. The colloidal iodine thus obtained was dialysed. The solution was negatively charged.

Our experiments showed that quantitatively there is no appreciable decrease in current density but with 0.0059 g. of the sol (Fig. 1) there is an effect on the crystal size and all the inherent defects of the plate disappear. If the quantity of the colloid is increased to 0.0118, the size of crystal increases and the deposit peels off easily.

FIG. 1.

Selenium sol.

FIG. 2.

Iodine sol.

Aluminium Hydroxide Sol.—A dilute solution of aluminium acetate (1% solution diluted twenty times) was warmed on a water-bath until the odour of acetic acid disappeared. The sol which resulted was very clear. It was carefully electrodialed. It was positively charged.

Like selenium there is an increase in the weight of the metal deposited. Addition of 0.001144 g. and 0.00572 g. sol respectively makes the deposit hard, bright, coherent and abrasion marks of the original plate disappear.

Ferric Hydroxide Sol.—Ammonium hydroxide added drop by drop to ferric chloride solution (5 c.c. saturated ferric chloride solution in 100 c.c. water) till the supernatant liquid acquired a red tinge. The precipitate was repeatedly washed and then transferred to an Erlenmeyer flask. About 40 c.c. of water were then added and the mixture shaken. 5 c.c. of this liquid were poured into 100 c.c. of water along with a few drops of *N/10*-HCl. On standing an intensely red solution was obtained. It was electrodialed and its charge was found to be positive.

Ferric hydroxide resembles selenium and aluminium hydroxide in its effects. The deposit becomes hard, close-grained and shining. The effect of addition of 0.00862 g. and 0.1724 g. of the colloid has been studied. Small crystals became visible and brightness diminished if the quantity of the sol is allowed to reach 0.02586 g.

It will be seen that in all the above cases small quantities of protective agents are employed to stabilize the colloids. These protective agents like

gum arabic, gelatin, tannin, etc., will have specific effects of their own. These effects, however, were not found to be comparable to those obtained above when these hydrophilic colloids alone were used. Microphotographs taken show that these agents are not so very active in the concentrations employed. Further the effects obtained are those from colloidal suspensions and not from the sols in the general sense of the word. As the bath is highly electrolytic in nature, formation of such a suspension is inevitable but it has been observed that this suspension takes days to settle and if stirring is constantly done, it sets hardly at all. That the colloids have a marked effect on the amount and the nature of the deposit appears to be beyond any doubt. The results are shown below.

TABLE I.

Effect of sols on the electrodeposition of nickel on copper.

Colloid.	Ni deposited.		Increase or decrease in C.D.	Amount of colloid per litre of bath soln.	Appearance of deposit.
	Actual.	Theoretical.			
Selenium	0'1246g.	0'1245g.	—	0'00 g.	Rough shining hard deposit; variation in size of crystals.
	0'1177	0'1136	Increase	0'00093	Closed and fine grained hard shining deposit; abrasion marks completely absent.
	0'1162	0'1134	Increase	0'00186	Do.
	0'1139	0'1102	Increase	0'00279	Bright deposit.
Sulphur	0'1734	0'1833	—	0'00	Deposit shining; abrasion marks quite visible.
	0'1149	0'1191	Decrease	0'002208	Velvety deposit of bluish black colour but shining deposit on the side not facing the anode.
	0'1187	0'1229 *	Decrease	0'004416	Do.
	0'1189	0'1232	Decrease	0'006624	Do
Iodine	0'1230	0'1232	—	0'00	Hard, lustrous deposit
	0'1175	0'1150	Decrease	0'0059	Shining and very hard deposit.

TABLE I (contd.).

Colloid.	Ni deposited		Increase or decrease in C. D.	Amount of colloid per litre of bath soln.	Appearance of deposit.
	Actual.	Theoretical.			
Al (OH) ₃	0'1122 g.	0'1190 g.	Decrease	0'0118 g.	Large flat crystals of varying size.
	0'0916	0'1187	Decrease	0'0177	Voluminous non-adherent crystals.
	0'1141	0'1150	—	0'00	...
	0'1157	0'1127	Increase	0'001144	Not very hard, non-coherent, bright deposit.
	0'1162	0'1130	Increase	0'00333	Very hard; all the abrasion marks absent, fine grained.
	0'1167	0'1130	Increase	0'00572	Bright deposit
Fe (OH) ₃	0'1246	0'1240	—	0'00	...
	0'1178	0'1143	Increase	0'00826	Close grained, hard shining deposit.
	0'1151	0'1126	Increase	0'01724	Fine grained, very hard and bright deposit.
	0'1124	0'1100	Increase	0'02568	Deposit hard but not bright.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
GOVERNMENT COLLEGE, LAHORE.

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